

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8200497>

***Abstract.** In the article today, in any educational institution that strives to maintain its vitality in the pedagogical conditions of innovative activity in the educational system, it is necessary to create something new in the field of science or in the personnel training system, to implement new ideas, i.e. materialization of ideas and involvement in the activities of educational institutions will ultimately create an opportunity for educational institutions to be financially self-sufficient. It shows that activation of the innovative activities of educational institutions has become an objective need along with the creation of an innovative environment that is effective on the scale of our republic.*

***Keywords:** innovative, integrative, individual, creative, approach, methodology, heuristic, constructive.*

In recent years, in our country, the development of scientific-theoretical and methodological foundations of teaching physics, the use of modern teaching techniques and methods during the lesson, the organization of an innovative educational environment, and the foundations of an innovative approach to education are being developed. "Increasing the volume and effectiveness of scientific and theoretical research in the field of physics, implementing additional measures to create the necessary scientific and pedagogical conditions for young researchers" is a priority task. For this reason, the development of new generation literature on teaching physics, the content of science and technology, educational literature and the current potential of production technology development, the methodology and collection of problem solving, and the methodology for performing laboratory work the possibility of creating manuals, electronic software products has increased.

Putting the problem situation into practice describes, first of all, directing the creative, heuristic, constructive thinking of the student to the activity. It serves as a pedagogical condition for acquiring new theoretical knowledge and forming practical skills that appear in the process of solving non-standard and standard problems. For this reason, the methodology of teaching the mechanics department of physics in technical higher education institutions should take into account the following practical stages of organizing students' educational activities: under the guidance of a pedagogue, students identify problematic situations (practical and experimental) in practical content, they should analyze, compare, choose, perform mathematical algorithmization of the problematic situation based on the application of mathematical apparatus familiar and understandable to them, and solve non-standard problems (experimental problems) based on the constructed algorithm [3].

It defines the tasks of defining the fundamental views on the education implemented in our country, the guidelines for increasing the effectiveness of the development of the organization of the educational process on a scientific and methodological basis, coordinating with the new pedagogical conditions and putting it into practice. The basis of this process is to teach students theoretical, practical, and independent knowledge of physics, practical skills and independent

experiments in applying theoretical knowledge of physics in the course of future professional-pedagogical activities. organizes professional-pedagogical activities aimed at creating performance skills. The content and tasks of this activity also serve to express the main goal of students who are being trained in higher education institutions [4].

It is important that innovation, the introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, and the creation of the necessary legal mechanisms in this regard are considered as a priority direction. At the same time, the system of training and certification of highly qualified scientific and scientific pedagogues is being further improved, and a number of innovations are being introduced to the post-university education stage. Also, certain works are being carried out based on the requirements of the times to increase the quality, scientific and practical importance of dissertation research.

The fact that the field of legal personnel training in our country is approached with such a progressive point of view will undoubtedly bring its bright results in the near future. After all, the decrees and decisions adopted in this regard, other legal documents, define specific measures aimed at training highly qualified legal personnel who meet the high requirements of the formation of civil society and modern international standards. And their performance is ensured without words and consistently.

Activities of implementation of innovations in educational processes

Preparing a teacher for innovative activities with a clear goal is a holistic process. It consists of interrelated and mutually conditioned periods: study and education in higher education institutions, as well as study in special institutions and post-higher education, which is organized on the basis of mutual exchange of practical pedagogical activities at school. Integration of the mentioned periods into the whole process of gradual development of the teacher's personality is the basis of including it in the pedagogical conditions of innovative activities in the educational system.

When creating the concept of preparing a teacher for innovative activities, systematic, reflexive-active, individual-creative approaches that ensure the design and implementation of the entire process of teacher personality formation are used as a basis.

For example, in terms of a systematic approach, all links of pedagogical education should maximally stimulate the emergence of all components of innovative activity in their entirety.

The implementation of the reflexive-active approach implies the development of the teacher's ability to enter into an active research position in order to critically analyze, reflect and evaluate the effectiveness of the teacher in relation to his own activity and the development of the student's personality as a subject of activity.

Figure 1. Pedagogical conditions of innovative activity as a result of establishment of integrated relations between educational institutions

The individual-creative approach brings the identification and formation of creative individuality in the teacher, the development of innovative consciousness in him to the personal level, which provides unique technology of activity.

The innovative readiness of the future teacher is his theoretical, practical and psychological-physiological level of mastering the full essence of pedagogical innovation in the conditions of continuous education. As a result of the pedagogic system, such preparation should help students to form a whole set of knowledge and skills in certain subjects and general professional activities based on ensuring the integrity of theory and practice, educating conscientious attitude to educational work, and developing creative activity.

Modern educational development has brought a new direction - innovative activity to the field. The term "innovative pedagogy" and research specific to it appeared in the 60s of the 20th century in Western Europe and the United States.

We can see the introduction of innovation into the education system in the content of education, teaching methods, lesson form, types of teaching, and teaching tools.

-Innovation in the educational content is explained by the introduction of traditional, non-traditional and distance teaching types.

- We see the introduction of active, passive and interactive methods of innovation into teaching methods. If the use of the active method serves to increase the activity of students in the course of the lesson, the passive method is explained by giving students a one-sided understanding.

- We can see the introduction of innovation into the form of lessons in the example of standard, non-standard and virtual lesson forms.

-Innovation in teaching types is explained by problem-based learning, heuristic learning, graded learning, integrated learning, interactive learning, informal learning, formal learning, non-formal learning.

- We will explain the introduction of innovation into teaching tools with the help of multimedia, electronic boards and other tools during the lesson.

Thus, this article has researched the pedagogical conditions of introducing innovation in the educational system, and certain works are being carried out based on the requirements of the times to increase its scientific and practical importance.

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